

This is the authors' version (post peer-review) of the manuscript:

T Pucher et al MDPI Nanomanufacturing 2023

[https://doi.org/ 10.3390/nanomanufacturing3030022](https://doi.org/10.3390/nanomanufacturing3030022)

That has been published in final form at:

<https://www.mdpi.com/2673-687X/3/3/22>

Low-cost shadow mask fabrication for nanoelectronics

Thomas Pucher ^{1,*}, Pablo Bastante ², Estrella Sánchez Viso ¹ and Andres Castellanos-Gomez ^{1,*}

¹ *Materials Science Factory. Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC), Madrid, E-28049, Spain*

² *Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, E-28049, Spain*

thomas.pucher@csic.es

andres.castellanos@csic.es

1 ABSTRACT

2 We present two approaches for fabricating shadow masks for the evaporation of electrodes
3 onto nanomaterials. In the first one, we combine the use of a commercial fiber laser engraving
4 system with readily available aluminum foil. This method is suitable for fabricating shadow
5 masks with line widths of 50 μm and minimum feature separation of 20 μm and it is very
6 straightforward to create masks with complex patterns. In the second approach, we use a
7 commercially available vinyl cutting machine to pattern a vinyl stencil mask and we use a
8 glass fiber to define the separation between the electrodes. With this approach we achieve
9 well-defined electrodes separated by 15 μm but this technique is less versatile to create
10 complex masks as compared with the laser-based one. We demonstrate the potential of these
11 techniques by fabricating field effect transistor devices based on MoS_2 . Our approach is a
12 cost-effective and easily accessible method for fabricating shadow masks with high
13 resolution and accuracy, making it accessible to a wider range of laboratories.

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Electrode deposition is a critical step in the fabrication of electronic devices with
3 nanomaterials. The most widely extended method to deposit electrodes is probably based in
4 lithographic techniques, i.e. photolithography or electron beam lithography, which require
5 specialized and expensive facilities as well as a strong technical background in micro-
6 fabrication. Recent works show different approaches for lower cost lithography setups used
7 with nanomaterials [1,2]. Nevertheless, these lithographic techniques require chemical
8 treatment steps to ensure the adhesion of the resists, for the development and the lift-off steps
9 which can harm certain nanomaterials that are more sensitive to the environment.

10 Direct metal evaporation through a shadow mask, on the other hand, has several advantages
11 over conventional lithographic techniques [3–6]. For example, it is relatively inexpensive,
12 easy to implement, and does not require a clean room environment. Additionally, it can be
13 easily applied in labs that do not have a background or infra-structure in microfabrication.
14 Another important aspect of the method is the fact that it is an ‘all-dry’ process, which means
15 that it is also compatible with nanomaterials that tend to degrade or damage during the
16 chemical and optical treatments involved in lithographic techniques [7–9]. Pre-patterned
17 electrodes have the advantage of enabling a nanomaterial-assembly in the glove box, which
18 is crucial for air-sensitive materials [10,11].

19 Typically, shadow mask fabrication requires a specialized facility similar to those used for
20 lithographic processing, which can be very costly [12,13]. Most research groups using
21 shadow mask deposition buy commercially available masks or outsource the fabrication to
22 micro-fabrication foundries, making the use of shadow mask deposition less flexible and not

1 suitable for rapid prototyping. This raises the question if there is a technique to fabricate
2 shadow masks in a way that is affordable and flexible, which would allow research groups
3 to design and fabricate their own customized masks without the need for costly infrastructure
4 or fabrication outsourcing.

5 Tomczyk et al. recently published a work about laser ablation fabrication of masks using
6 homebuilt optical systems, however these systems were typically composed of expensive
7 components and the resolution achieved was only in the 50 to 100 μm range [14]. This may
8 not be sufficient for many applications with nanomaterials which require electrodes in the
9 10-50 μm range. Moreover, the reported laser ablation setups are difficult to use and
10 expensive to implement making it not suitable for many research groups. Elhami Nik et al.
11 also reported a recent work about the use of CO₂ laser to ab-late filter paper to create shadow
12 masks resulting in masks with minimum feature size of 100 μm [15].

13 In this work, we present two approaches for fabricating shadow masks for the evaporation of
14 electrodes to fabricate devices with nanomaterials, bridging the gap between flexibility in
15 design realization and cost-factor. In the first method we make use of a commercially
16 available fiber laser engraving system (Atomstack M4, costing less than 1100€) with readily
17 available metal supports (standard kitchen aluminum foil, thick aluminum foil) for shadow
18 mask engraving of self-drafted layouts with maximum flexibility. In the second method we
19 use a vinyl cutting machine (Cricut Maker 3, under 500€) to create a vinyl stencil mask
20 defining the electrodes and pads with pre-defined gap sizes and maximum cost effectiveness.
21 As the resolution of the vinyl cutter does not allow to achieve electrode separation under 100
22 μm , we place a glass fiber (15 μm in diameter) to define the separation between the

1 electrodes. We illustrate the potential of these methods by fabricating single-layer MoS₂ field
2 effect transistors.

3 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

4 Figure 1a shows a picture of the compact fiber laser engraving system used in this work while
5 it cuts through an aluminum foil. The system uses a pulsed IR laser (1064 nm) focused on a
6 spot of ~20 μm and featuring two scanning galvanometer mirrors that allow reaching a
7 marking speed of up to 12 m/s. We found that standard kitchen aluminum foil can be used to
8 fabricate well defined shadow masks but handling them without creating folds/wrinkles can
9 be challenging (note that an example of a kitchen aluminum foil mask is given in the
10 supporting information). We thus tested thicker aluminum foil (40 μm thick, 150 x 150 mm
11 sheets, typically commercialized for their use in shisha/hookah, [LINK](#)) that leads to an
12 optimal performance in terms of easiness to pattern and to handle afterwards. Figure 1b
13 shows a picture of one of these thick aluminum foils, laser cut to form a shadow mask with
14 pads and drain-source electrodes separated by different gap sides, adhered to a SiO₂/Si
15 substrate with kapton tape prior metal evaporation. The inset in the figure shows a higher
16 magnification image of one of the 20 μm gaps. We found that masks with designed drain-
17 source separation under 20 μm tend to fail, thus leading to a shorted drain-source connection.
18 Figure 1c shows a picture of the other system tested to fabricate inexpensive homemade
19 shadow masks: a vinyl cutter. The system operates very similarly to an old-fashion XY plotter
20 system but using a sharp blade tool instead of a pen. This kind of system, although
21 inexpensive and very easy to use, cannot be used to make small features or structures with
22 small pitch (that is, below 200 μm feature or pitch size the vinyl-cut masks are not reliable).
23 To fabricate shadow masks with smaller separation between drain and source electrodes we

1 combined the vinyl-cut mask with a glass fiber that is 15 μm in diameter to define the
2 separation between drain and source electrodes without being limited by the vinyl cutting
3 system. Previous works using glass or carbon fibers as shadow masks have been reported in
4 the literature providing good quality electrodes [16,17]. The combination with the vinyl cut
5 mask can provide a more controlled way to deposit the metal electrodes and to pattern the
6 pads and the leads to avoid shorts with other parts of the device or with the back gate. Figure
7 1d shows an optical image of one of the vinyl cut masks where one can appreciate the pads
8 and the electrode leads. One can also notice the glass fiber deposited in the central part of the
9 substrate before adhering the vinyl cut mask to define the drain-source separation. The inset
10 shows a higher magnification image of the glass fiber creating the separation between the
11 electrodes.

12

1 **Figure 1: Fabrication of shadow masks with commercially available laser engraver and vinyl**
2 **cutter systems.** (a) Picture of a fiber laser engraving system Atomstack M4 while cutting a thick
3 aluminum foil. (b) Picture of one of the fabricated shadow masks with drain and source electrodes
4 separated by different distances ranging from 20 μm to 40 μm , fixed on a SiO₂/Si substrate with
5 kapton tape. (Inset) Optical microscopy image of the separation between the drain and source
6 electrode at the central part of the ‘bar shaped’ lead. The scale bar is 100 μm . (c) Picture of a Cricut
7 Maker 3 vinyl cutter system used to prepare a vinyl stencil mask with the pads and the electrode leads.
8 (d) Vinyl mask adhered onto a SiO₂/Si substrate using the adhesive of the vinyl. A 15 μm diameter
9 glass fiber was deposited onto the surface prior adhering the mask to define the separation between
10 drain and source electrodes (see inset, scale bar: 500 μm).

11

12 **RESULTS**

13 **Fabrication of electrodes by metal deposition through the masks**

14 In the following we characterize the electrodes achieved after metal deposition through the
15 shadow masks. We employ an electron beam evaporation system to de-posit 5 nm of Ti
16 (adhesion layer) and 45 nm of Au. Figure 2a shows an optical image of a shadow mask
17 fabricated onto the 40 μm thick aluminum foil by laser ablation. Figure 2b shows an optical
18 image of a SiO₂/Si substrate after metal deposition that closely follows the shape of the
19 shadow mask shown in Figure 2a. The inset in Figure 2b shows a higher magnification optical
20 microscopy image of the gap between drain and source electrodes. Figure 2c shows an
21 optical image of a mask made with the combination of a glass fiber and a vinyl cut stencil.
22 The mask is adhered on a SiO₂/Si substrate before metal deposition. Figure 2d is an optical
23 image of the SiO₂/Si substrate after metal deposition. The inset in 2d depicts a detail of the
24 gap created between drain and source with the glass fiber.

25 As one can clearly see from Figure 2, we found that the vinyl + glass fiber approach yields
26 very well-defined drain-source electrodes whose separation is directly defined by the
27 diameter of the fiber. But this technique suffers of lower flexibility to explore different
28 customized electrodes design. The laser engraving method, on the other hand, yields poorly

1 defined electrode edges but ensures complete flexibility over the pattern design. This
2 increased flexibility allows for the design and implementation of new patterns and layouts,
3 providing more freedom in the design process and enabling more advanced electronic devices
4 to be fabricated with nanomaterials. Additionally, this method can be used to quickly test
5 different designs, which will allow for faster development and optimization of the fabrication
6 process. In this way, the use of a commercially available fiber laser engraving system can
7 open the door to additional flexibility in shadow mask fabrication, providing a powerful tool
8 for researchers working in the field of nanoelectronics, whereas the use of a vinyl cutter in
9 combination with glass fibers can provide the most cost-effective route to fabricate devices
10 in research groups running under a moderate budget. We address the reader to Figure S2 in
11 the Supporting Information for an atomic force microscopy (AFM) characterization of the
12 electrodes fabricated with these shadow masks as well as with a commercially available
13 shadow mask (Ossila E321).

1

2 **Figure 2: Resulting electrodes after evaporation through the homebuilt shadow masks.** (a)
 3 Optical microscopy image of a drain-source mask patterned on a thick aluminum foil with the fiber
 4 laser engraver system. (b) Optical microscopy image of the resulting electrodes after evaporating Au
 5 (45 nm)/Ti (5 nm) onto a SiO₂/Si substrate. (Inset) Higher magnification image of the gap between
 6 drain and source electrodes. (c) Optical microscopy image of a drain-source mask fabricated by
 7 combining the vinyl mask with a 15 μm diameter glass fiber, adhered onto a SiO₂/Si before metal
 8 deposition. (d) Optical microscopy image of the resulting electrodes after evaporating Au (45 nm)/Ti
 9 (5 nm) onto a SiO₂/Si substrate. (Inset) Higher magnification image of the gap between drain and
 10 source electrodes.

11

12 **Example of devices fabricated with the shadow masks**

13 In order to illustrate the potential of these techniques to fabricate devices, we have deposited
 14 single-layer MoS₂ flakes bridging the electrodes fabricated by metal deposition through the
 15 shadow masks. We employed a viscoelastic dry-transfer method based on Gel-Film stamps
 16 [18] to transfer a single-layer MoS₂ flake bridging drain and source electrodes [19,20].

1 Figure 3a and 3c show optical microscopy images of devices fabricated with electrodes
2 deposited through laser ablated and vinyl+fiber shadow masks, respectively. After flake
3 deposition, we perform a vacuum annealing step [2 h, 200 °C, 10-3 mbar] to improve the
4 metal-semiconductor contact. We tested the electronic properties of the devices in a
5 homebuilt probe station. Figure 3b and 3d show the source-drain current as a function of the
6 back-gate voltage measured on the devices shown in 3a and 3c. The transfer curves were
7 measured under a constant source-drain bias VDS of 1 V with a gate voltage step speed of 1
8 Vs⁻¹ (sweeping from -60 V to +60 V).

9 From these measurements one can extract the field-effect mobility (μFE) of the fabricated
10 field effect transistors following the expression [21]:

$$11 \quad \mu_{FE} = \frac{dI_{DS}}{dV_G} \frac{L}{W} \frac{1}{C_G \cdot V_{DS}} ,$$

12 where I_{DS}, V_{DS} and V_{GS} are the source-drain current, source-drain voltage and the gate
13 voltage, C_G is the capacitance of the silicon oxide dielectric, L and W are the length and
14 width of the transistor channel. The devices shown in Figure 3 presented a mobility of 0.94
15 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (laser-ablation mask) and 10.7 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (vinyl+fiber masks). In the Supporting
16 Information Figure S3 the reader will find the results of another two devices showing
17 mobilities of 1 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (for laser-ablation mask) and 0.39 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (for vinyl+fiber masks).
18 These field effect measurements have been carried out in three-terminal configuration,
19 without discounting for the effect of the contact resistance, and thus the mobility values
20 obtained here should be considered as low-er-bound estimates as discounting for the contact
21 resistance would lead to larger mobilities. It is interesting to note that we found that devices
22 fabricated with electrodes fabricated by deposition through commercially available shadow

1 masks (Ossila E321) lead to devices with similar characteristics in terms of threshold voltage,
 2 mobility and current ON/OFF values achieved by our group [22,23] as well as others [24–
 3 27], with typical mobility values below $10 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ with SiO_2 as the dielectric material.
 4 Overcoming these values and getting closer to MoS₂'s theoretical limit of around $200 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$
 5 s^{-1} would mean a change to a dielectric material with higher dielectric constant [21,22,28].
 6 Similarly, other transistor architectures can be designed, such as simple complete bottom gate
 7 tunnel field effect transistors [29,30] or anywhere where pre-patterned electrodes are
 8 applicable with consideration of the achievable feature sizes.

9

10 **Figure 3: Example of nanomaterial-based devices based on the electrodes fabricated with the**
 11 **homemade shadow masks.** (a) Optical microscopy image of a single-layer MoS₂ flake bridging the

1 drain and source electrodes fabricated with the laser ablated shadow mask. (b) Semi-logarithmic
2 transfer curve of the resulting MoS₂ field effect transistor for a constant bias V_{DS} of 1 V. (Inset)
3 Gate-dependent IVs for gate voltages of -60 to 60 V. (c) Optical microscopy image a single-layer
4 MoS₂ flake transferred bridging the drain and source electrodes fabricated with vinyl + glass fiber
5 mask. (d) Semi-logarithmic transfer curve of the resulting MoS₂ field effect transistor for a constant
6 bias V_{DS} of 0.5 V. (Inset) Gate-dependent IVs for gate voltages of -60 to 60 V.

7

8 **Examples of shadow masks with more complex patterns**

9 Figure 4 shows few examples of other shadow mask designs fabricated with the laser ablation
10 method on 40 μm thick aluminum foil to illustrate the flexibility of this technique for rapid
11 prototyping of devices. These patterns are chosen due to their usefulness when studying
12 nanomaterials-based devices: a Hall bar, a four-terminal mask and a mask designed to test
13 in-plane electrical anisotropy.

14

15 **Figure 4: Examples of different shadow mask patterns created with the fiber laser engraving**
16 **system.** (a) Hall bar. (b) 4-terminal configuration. (c) Electrode probes to test in-plane anisotropic
17 materials.

18

19 **DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS**

20 We have presented two different approaches for fabricating shadow masks for the
21 evaporation of electrodes onto nanomaterials using a commercially available fiber laser
22 engraving system or a vinyl cutting machine. Laser engraving of aluminum foil is able to
23 produce shadow masks with line widths of 50 μm and minimum feature separation of 20 μm,

1 although with a noticeable edge roughness, and with complete flexibility over the pattern
2 design. In the second technique we use the vinyl cutter to define the pads and electrode leads
3 but we place a glass fiber to create a well-defined narrow separation between drain and source
4 electrodes. This technique allows us to create line widths of $200\ \mu\text{m}$ separated by $15\ \mu\text{m}$
5 (dependent on the glass fiber diameter) with a very sharp and well-defined electrode
6 separation. Nonetheless, the vinyl + fiber technique is less flexible than the laser engraving
7 one in terms of prototyping. We have proven the potential of these techniques by fabricating
8 devices based on MoS₂. A set of different patterns shows the ability of extending this
9 technique to various applications in the field of microelectronics, without limitation of
10 substrate type and the freedom of post material assembly due to pre-patterned structures. By
11 using this method, patterns on flexible substrates can enable measurements in the field of
12 strain engineering or biomedical applications. Our approaches are cost-effective and easily
13 accessible methods for fabricating shadow masks with high resolution and accuracy, making
14 it accessible to a wider range of laboratories. This work contributes a valuable addition to the
15 field of nanoelectronics by providing simple and inexpensive methods for fabricating high-
16 resolution shadow masks.

17

18 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

19 Conceptualization, A.C. and T.P.; methodology, T.P. and P.B.; software, T.P.; validation,
20 T.P. and A.C.; formal analysis, T.P. and P.B.; data curation, T.P., P.B. and E.S.V.; writing—
21 original draft preparation, A.C.; writing—review and editing, A.C. and T.P.; visualization,
22 T.P., A.C. and E.S.V.; supervision, A.C.. All authors have read and agreed to the published
23 version of the manuscript.

1

2 **DATA AVAILIBLTY**

3 The data of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

4 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

5 We thank Gulsum Ersu for her valuable help during the video shoot for the supporting infor-
6 mation. This work was funded by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European
7 Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement n° 755655, ERC-
8 StG 2017 project 2D-TOPSENSE), and the Ministry of Science and Innovation (Spain)
9 through the projects PID2020-115566RB-I00 and TED2021-132267B-I00. We also
10 acknowledge funding from the EU FLAG-ERA project To2Dox (JTC-2019-009) and the
11 Comunidad de Madrid through the CAIRO-CM project (Y2020/NMT-6661). ChatGPT
12 (GPT-3.5, OpenAI's large-scale language-generation model) has been used to improve the
13 English grammar and writing style of this manuscript. The authors have reviewed, edited,
14 and revised the ChatGPT generated texts to their own liking and take ultimate responsibility
15 for the content of this publication [31].

16 **AUTHOR INFORMATION**

17 **Corresponding Authors**

18 Thomas Pucher thomas.pucher@csic.es

19 Andres Castellanos-Gomez andres.castellanos@csic.es

20 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

21 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

1 REFERENCES

- 2 1. Pugachev, M.V.; Duleba, A.I.; Galiullin, A.A.; Kuntsevich, A.Y. Micromask
3 Lithography for Cheap and Fast 2D Materials Microstructures Fabrication. *Micromachines*
4 2021, 12, 850, doi:10.3390/mi12080850.
- 5 2. Khan, M.S.; Lachmayer, R.; Roth, B. Maskless Lithography for Versatile and Low
6 Cost Fabrication of Polymer Based Micro Optical Structures. *OSA Continuum* 2020, 3,
7 2808, doi:10.1364/OSAC.400056.
- 8 3. Zhou, Y.X.; Johnson, A.T.; Hone, J.; Smith, W.F. Simple Fabrication of Molecular
9 Circuits by Shadow Mask Evaporation. *Nano Lett.* 2003, 3, 1371–1374,
10 doi:10.1021/nl034512y.
- 11 4. Tien, D.H.; Park, J.-Y.; Kim, K.B.; Lee, N.; Seo, Y. Characterization of Graphene-
12 Based FET Fabricated Using a Shadow Mask. *Scientific reports* 2016, 6, 25050,
13 doi:10.1038/srep25050.
- 14 5. Bao, W.; Liu, G.; Zhao, Z.; Zhang, H.; Yan, D.; Deshpande, A.; LeRoy, B.; Lau,
15 C.N. Lithography-Free Fabrication of High Quality Substrate-Supported and Freestanding
16 Graphene Devices. *Nano Research* 2010, 3, 98–102, doi:10.1007/s12274-010-1013-5.
- 17 6. Yun, H.; Kim, S.; Kim, H.; Lee, J.; McAllister, K.; Kim, J.; Pyo, S.; Sung Kim, J.;
18 Campbell, E.E.B.; Hyung Lee, W.; et al. Stencil Nano Lithography Based on a Nanoscale
19 Polymer Shadow Mask: Towards Organic Nanoelectronics. *Scientific reports* 2015, 5,
20 10220, doi:10.1038/srep10220.
- 21 7. Liang, J.; Xu, K.; Toncini, B.; Bersch, B.; Jariwala, B.; Lin, Y.; Robinson, J.;
22 Fullerton-Shirey, S.K. Impact of Post-Lithography Polymer Residue on the Electrical
23 Characteristics of MoS₂ and WSe₂ Field Effect Transistors. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 2019,
24 6, 1801321, doi:10.1002/admi.201801321.
- 25 8. Shen, X.; Wang, H.; Yu, T. How Do the Electron Beam Writing and Metal
26 Deposition Affect the Properties of Graphene during Device Fabrication? *Nanoscale* 2013,
27 5, 3352, doi:10.1039/c3nr33460k.
- 28 9. Katagiri, Y.; Nakamura, T.; Ishii, A.; Ohata, C.; Hasegawa, M.; Katsumoto, S.;
29 Cusati, T.; Fortunelli, A.; Iannaccone, G.; Fiori, G.; et al. Gate-Tunable Atomically Thin
30 Lateral MoS₂ Schottky Junction Patterned by Electron Beam. *Nano Lett.* 2016, 16, 3788–
31 3794, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.6b01186.
- 32 10. Cao, Y.; Mishchenko, A.; Yu, G.L.; Khestanova, E.; Rooney, A.P.; Prestat, E.;
33 Kretinin, A.V.; Blake, P.; Shalom, M.B.; Woods, C.; et al. Quality Heterostructures from
34 Two-Dimensional Crystals Unstable in Air by Their Assembly in Inert Atmosphere. *Nano*
35 *Lett.* 2015, 15, 4914–4921, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.5b00648.
- 36 11. Castellanos-Gomez, A.; Vicarelli, L.; Prada, E.; Island, J.O.; Narasimha-Acharya,
37 K.L.; Blanter, S.I.; Groenendijk, D.J.; Buscema, M.; Steele, G.A.; Alvarez, J.V.; et al.

- 1 Isolation and Characterization of Few-Layer Black Phosphorus. *2D Mater.* 2014, 1,
2 025001, doi:10.1088/2053-1583/1/2/025001.
- 3 12. Aljada, M.; Mutkins, K.; Vamvounis, G.; Burn, P.; Meredith, P. High Quality
4 Shadow Masks for Top Contact Organic Field Effect Transistors Using Deep Reactive Ion
5 Etching. *J. Micromech. Microeng.* 2010, 20, 075037, doi:10.1088/0960-1317/20/7/075037.
- 6 13. Zhang, H.; Guo, X.; Niu, W.; Xu, H.; Wu, Q.; Liao, F.; Chen, J.; Tang, H.; Liu, H.;
7 Xu, Z.; et al. Multilayer Si Shadow Mask Processing of Wafer-Scale MoS₂ Devices. *2D*
8 *Mater.* 2020, 7, 025019, doi:10.1088/2053-1583/ab6b6b.
- 9 14. Tomczyk, M.; Kubik, P.; Waliszewski, W. Optimization of the Ablative Laser
10 Cutting of Shadow Mask for Organic FET Electrode Fabrication. *Electronics* 2020, 9,
11 2184, doi:10.3390/electronics9122184.
- 12 15. Elhami Nik, F.; Matthiesen, I.; Herland, A.; Winkler, T. Low-Cost PVD Shadow
13 Masks with Submillimeter Resolution from Laser-Cut Paper. *Micromachines* 2020, 11,
14 676, doi:10.3390/mi11070676.
- 15 16. Staley, N.; Wang, H.; Puls, C.; Forster, J.; Jackson, T.N.; McCarthy, K.; Clouser,
16 B.; Liu, Y. Lithography-Free Fabrication of Graphene Devices. *Applied Physics Letters*
17 2007, 90, 143518.
- 18 17. Castellanos-Gomez, A.; Smit, R.H.M.; Agraït, N.; Rubio-Bollinger, G. Spatially
19 Resolved Electronic Inhomogeneities of Graphene Due to Subsurface Charges. *Carbon*
20 2012, 50, 932–938, doi:10.1016/j.carbon.2011.09.055.
- 21 18. Castellanos-Gomez, A.; Buscema, M.; Molenaar, R.; Singh, V.; Janssen, L.; van der
22 Zant, H.S.J.; Steele, G.A. Deterministic Transfer of Two-Dimensional Materials by All-Dry
23 Viscoelastic Stamping. *2D Materials* 2014, 1, 011002, doi:10.1088/2053-1583/1/1/011002.
- 24 19. Yang, R.; Zheng, X.; Wang, Z.; Miller, C.J.; Feng, P.X.-L. Multilayer MoS₂
25 Transistors Enabled by a Facile Dry-Transfer Technique and Thermal Annealing. *Journal*
26 *of Vacuum Science & Technology B, Nanotechnology and Microelectronics: Materials,*
27 *Processing, Measurement, and Phenomena* 2014, 32, 61203.
- 28 20. Frisenda, R.; Navarro-Moratalla, E.; Gant, P.; De Lara, D.P.; Jarillo-Herrero, P.;
29 Gorbachev, R.V.; Castellanos-Gomez, A. Recent Progress in the Assembly of Nanodevices
30 and van Der Waals Heterostructures by Deterministic Placement of 2D Materials. *Chemical*
31 *Society Reviews* 2018, 47, 53–68.
- 32 21. Radisavljevic, B.; Radenovic, A.; Brivio, J.; Giacometti, V.; Kis, A. Single-Layer
33 MoS₂ Transistors. *Nature Nanotechnology* 2011, 6, doi:10.1038/nnano.2010.279.
- 34 22. Puebla, S.; Pucher, T.; Rouco, V.; Sanchez-Santolino, G.; Xie, Y.; Zamora, V.;
35 Cuellar, F.A.; Mompean, F.J.; Leon, C.; Island, J.O.; et al. Combining Freestanding
36 Ferroelectric Perovskite Oxides with Two-Dimensional Semiconductors for High

- 1 Performance Transistors. *Nano Lett.* 2022, 22, 7457–7466,
2 doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.2c02395.
- 3 23. Xie, Y.; Çakıroğlu, O.; Hu, W.; He, K.; Puebla, S.; Pucher, T.; Zhao, Q.; Ma, X.;
4 Munuera, C.; Castellanos-Gomez, A. Laser Trimming for Lithography-Free Fabrications of
5 MoS₂ Devices. *Nano Res.* 2023, 16, 5042–5046, doi:10.1007/s12274-022-5241-2.
- 6 24. Qiu, H.; Pan, L.; Yao, Z.; Li, J.; Shi, Y.; Wang, X. Electrical Characterization of
7 Back-Gated Bi-Layer MoS₂ Field-Effect Transistors and the Effect of Ambient on Their
8 Performances. *Applied Physics Letters* 2012, 100, 123104, doi:10.1063/1.3696045.
- 9 25. Late, D.J.; Liu, B.; Matte, H.S.S.R.; Dravid, V.P.; Rao, C.N.R. Hysteresis in Single-
10 Layer MoS₂ Field Effect Transistors. *ACS Nano* 2012, 6, 5635–5641,
11 doi:10.1021/nn301572c.
- 12 26. Ghatak, S.; Pal, A.N.; Ghosh, A. Nature of Electronic States in Atomically Thin
13 MoS₂ Field-Effect Transistors. *ACS Nano* 2011, 5, 7707–7712, doi:10.1021/nn202852j.
- 14 27. Li, T.; Du, G.; Zhang, B.; Zeng, Z. Scaling Behavior of Hysteresis in Multilayer
15 MoS₂ Field Effect Transistors. *Applied Physics Letters* 2014, 105, 093107,
16 doi:10.1063/1.4894865.
- 17 28. Yoon, Y.; Ganapathi, K.; Salahuddin, S. How Good Can Monolayer MoS₂
18 Transistors Be? *Nano Lett.* 2011, 11, 3768–3773, doi:10.1021/nl2018178.
- 19 29. Nourbakhsh, A.; Zubair, A.; Dresselhaus, M.S.; Palacios, T. Transport Properties of
20 a MoS₂/WSe₂ Heterojunction Transistor and Its Potential for Application. *Nano Lett.*
21 2016, 16, 1359–1366, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.5b04791.
- 22 30. Balaji, Y.; Smets, Q.; Szabo, Á.; Mascaro, M.; Lin, D.; Asselberghs, I.; Radu, I.;
23 Luisier, M.; Groeseneken, G. MoS₂/MoTe₂ Heterostructure Tunnel FETs Using Gated
24 Schottky Contacts. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2020, 30, 1905970, doi:10.1002/adfm.201905970.
- 25 31. Castellanos-Gomez, A. Good Practices for Scientific Article Writing with ChatGPT
26 and Other Artificial Intelligence Language Models. *Nanomanufacturing* 2023, 3, 135–138,
27 doi:10.3390/nanomanufacturing3020009.

28

1

Supporting Information:

Low-cost shadow mask fabrication for nanoelectronics

Thomas Pucher ^{1,*}, Pablo Bastante ², Estrella Sánchez Viso ¹ and Andres Castellanos-Gomez ^{1,*}

¹ Materials Science Factory. Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC), Madrid, E-28049, Spain

² Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, E-28049, Spain

thomas.pucher@csic.es

andres.castellanos@csic.es

2

3

4 **Figure S1: Mask fabrication on standard kitchen aluminum foil.** Left: Still of used aluminum foil
5 and mask after laser writing. Right: Detailed image of the same foil mask with six electrode pairs.
6 The inset shows a microscope image of created 20 μm gap.

7

8

1
2
3
4
5
6
7

Figure S2: Atomic force characterization of the electrodes fabricated with different techniques. (a) Deposition through a shadow mask fabricated on thick aluminum foil patterned with a fiber laser. (b) Deposition through mask fabricated with a vinyl and a 15 μm diameter glass fiber. (c) Electrodes fabricated by deposition through a commercially available shadow mask from Ossila (part number E321).

8
9
10
11
12

Figure S3: More examples of nanomaterial-based devices based on the electrodes fabricated with the homemade shadow masks. (a) Optical microscopy image of a single-layer MoS₂ flake transferred bridging the drain and source electrodes fabricated with the laser ablated shadow mask. (b) Drain-source current vs. gate voltage curve of the resulting MoS₂ field effect transistor. (c) Drain-

- 1 source current vs. bias voltage curves at different gate voltages. (d) Optical microscopy image of a
- 2 single-layer MoS₂ flake transferred bridging the drain and source electrodes fabricated with vinyl +
- 3 glass fiber mask. (e) Drain-source current vs. gate voltage curve of the resulting MoS₂ field effect
- 4 transistor. (f) Drain-source current vs. bias voltage curves at different gate voltages.